

Managing well	245	41.7	415	42.3	255	34.4	376	41.7	352	50.8
Vulnerable	124	21.1	229	23.3	178	24.0	170	18.9	167	24.1
Mildly frail	91	15.5	158	16.1	125	16.8	171	19.0	115	16.6
Moderately frail	84	14.3	139	14.2	144	19.4	92	10.2	46	6.6
Severely frail	21	3.6	28	2.9	19	2.6	23	2.5	6	0.9
Very severely frail	2	0.3	2	0.2	4	0.5	0	0.0	0	0.00
Physical health composite score, median (range)	509	36.7 (13-62)	948	35.9 (12-63)	713	35.0 (11-62)	675	38.7 (11-68)	639	37.5 (10-60)
Mental health composite score, median (range)	506	47.6 (16-74)	946	48.6 (12-72)	715	47.5 (17-76)	676	46.8 (14-72)	640	53.5 (16-74)
Substances <8	259	44.1	351	35.8	334	45.0	439	48.7	261	37.7
≥10	328	55.9	630	64.2	408	55.0	462	51.3	432	62.3
n (mean ±SD)	587	10.4 ±2.3	981	10.9 ±2.7	742	10.4 ±2.4	901	10.0 ±2.0	693	10.9 ±2.7
Diagnoses, n (mean ±SD)	587	8.5±3.5	981	12.9 ±6.2	742	10.4 ±4.5	901	7.6 ±2.7	693	6.8 ±3.5

Legend: BMI= Body Mass Index, Germany 1= Rostock, Germany 2= Witten, SD= Standard deviation